

The Role of Institutional Strength in Enhancing the Effect of International Financial Reporting Standards on FDI Attraction in Nigeria

Dr Johnbest Churchill Ologhodo
National Open University of Nigeria
Financial Studies Department
jologhodo@noun.edu.ng
08033799757

Dr David Ugbaje Ojofedo
Nasarawa State University, Keffi
Accounting Department
ugbajedavidojofedo@gmail.com
08062239432

Dr Bukola Helen Odekunle
Nasarawa State University, Keffi
Accounting Department
Bukkyodekunle12@gmail.com
08065784009

Abstract

This study examines the role of institutional strength in enhancing the impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption on foreign direct investment (FDI) attraction in Nigeria. The study specifically investigates the relationship between IFRS adoption and foreign investment in equity, money market portfolios, and suppliers' credit. Anchored on investment and institutional theories, the study adopts a descriptive research design using secondary data covering the period 2015–2023, corresponding with Nigeria's IFRS implementation phase. Data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria and the World Bank Worldwide Governance Indicators database. The Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) panel estimation technique was employed to address potential endogeneity and dynamic relationships among the variables. The findings indicate that IFRS adoption alone does not significantly attract foreign investment. However, its effectiveness improves when supported by strong institutional factors such as political stability and effective corruption control. While IFRS enhances financial transparency and comparability, foreign investors are more responsive to governance credibility and a stable political environment. The study concludes that IFRS adoption should be complemented with strong institutional reforms to effectively attract and sustain foreign investment inflows in Nigeria.

Keywords: Institutional Quality; IFRS Adoption; Foreign Direct Investment (FDI); Political Stability; Corruption Control

JEL Classification: F38; P33; G15

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

1. Introduction

Globalization has significantly reshaped international trade and investment flows, increased the interdependence of national economies and heightened the need for transparent and comparable financial reporting standards. To address disparities in accounting practices across countries, the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) introduced the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) with the objective of promoting clarity, uniformity, and credibility in financial reporting. The implementation of IFRS is expected to improve the quality of financial disclosures (Al-Tuwaijari et al, 2025; Khan et al., 2024), reduce information asymmetry among stakeholders, and strengthen investor confidence factors that encourage the inflow of foreign direct investment (FDI).

FDI plays a central role in economic development, particularly in emerging economies, as it brings capital, technology, and managerial expertise. While IFRS adoption has been associated with increased financial transparency, which theoretically supports higher FDI inflows, empirical evidence shows that its effectiveness varies across countries. This variation is often linked to the strength of a country's institutional environment.

Although Nigeria has implemented IFRS with the aim of attracting more foreign investment, the anticipated growth in FDI inflows has not been consistently realized. This suggests that institutional quality reflected in governance efficiency, regulatory enforcement, and the control of corruption may influence the extent to which IFRS contributes to investment attraction. Therefore, this study examines the role of institutional strength in enhancing the effects of IFRS adoption on FDI inflows in Nigeria, with specific attention to equity investment, money market flows, and suppliers' credit. This is particularly strengthened by the following composite objectives, which are: 1) to determine whether the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) have any significant relationship with foreign investment in equity; 2) to show how international financial reporting standard effectively influence foreign investment in money market. 3). to examine whether International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) practice attract foreign investment in suppliers' credit potentials. The study is underpinned by the investment and institutional theories.

1.1. Statement of the problem

Although previous research has explored the impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption on foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria, many studies including Nzube and Emmanuel (2018), Adeleye et al., (2021) tend to examine investment inflows in aggregate terms, often merging direct and portfolio investments. Such aggregation reduces the clarity and specificity of their findings and may obscure the heterogeneous responses of different forms of foreign capital to accounting reforms. Recent studies have also noted that the use of aggregate capital inflow measures may mask the differential behaviour of various investment categories and limit the precision of empirical conclusions (e.g., Okafor & Arowoshegbe, 2021; Odoemelam, et al., 2022; Williams, 2025). To overcome this limitation, the present study separates investment into distinct components, including equity inflows, money market investments, and suppliers'

credit. This disaggregation allows for a more precise analysis of how IFRS adoption influences different forms of foreign capital inflows.

Moreover, the attraction of FDI is not determined by accounting transparency alone. Non-accounting factors such as political stability, regulatory effectiveness, security of property rights, and macroeconomic stability play essential roles in shaping investment decisions. Contemporary literature increasingly emphasizes that the effectiveness of financial reporting reforms depends largely on the surrounding institutional environment (Khan et al., 2024; Boateng et al., 2021; Nnadi & Soobaroyen, 2023). Strong institutional frameworks improve the credibility of financial disclosures and reduce information asymmetry faced by foreign investors. Recognizing this, the study introduces institutional strength as a moderating factor in the relationship between IFRS adoption and FDI inflows to bridge this gap. Institutional strength reflected in governance efficiency, regulatory quality, judicial independence, and the rule of law has the potential to enhance the credibility and usefulness of financial reporting, thereby increasing investor confidence. However, existing studies by Audu and Otokiti, 2025; Williams, 2025). rarely integrate this dimension within the Nigerian context, despite its importance

Methodologically, this study contributes to the literature by employing the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) panel estimation technique. GMM is appropriate for capturing the dynamic structure of FDI inflows, as it incorporates lagged dependent variables and addresses challenges such as endogeneity and autocorrelation that earlier studies often overlooked. Recent empirical studies on international investment flows increasingly recommend dynamic panel approaches such as GMM for improving estimation reliability in macro-financial relationships (Sovbetov, 2025; Adeleye, 2 et al., 2021). By applying this approach, the study provides more rigorous and reliable evidence on how institutional strength enhances the effectiveness of IFRS adoption in attracting sustained FDI into Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual framework

2.1.1. Adoption of IFRS

The adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) refers to the transitioning by nations, institutions, or corporations from their domestic accounting frameworks to the preparation and presentation of financial statements in line with IFRS guidelines. Developed by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), IFRS serves as a globally accepted framework aimed at endorsing transparency, consistency, and comparability in financial reporting across international boundaries (Istiak et al., 2024).

2.1.2. Corruption control

According to El-Helaly (2020) corruption control is the strategic efforts and mechanisms implemented to prevent, detect and reduce corruption within society, organizations or governments. It involves the establishment of ethical standards, institutional framework sand

accountability measures to ensure integrity, transparency and efficiency in public and private management.

Corruption refers to the misapplication of entrusted authority for own advantage. It can appear in several forms, such as inducement, misappropriation, discrimination, favoritism, and fraud. The main goal of corruption control is to curb these unethical practices and tackle the underlying factors that enable them.

2.1.3. Political stability

Radu (2015), believed political stability is a means by which peoples' perception are measured in relation to the likelihood to which the national government will be disrupted, destabilized or toppled by those opposed to the government of the day through non-constitutional or forcefully. It is the condition where a government functions effectively without significant disruptions, conflicts or threats to its authority, ensuring a predictable and secured environment for citizens, businesses and institutions. It usually involves the absence of widespread violence, protests, or coup de tat, along with consistent policies and governance. According to Houque et al., (2024) identify political stability to be associated with: strong institutions, political trust, economic growth, social harmony among others that will heighten the confidence of both citizens and foreign.

2.1.4. Institutional quality

The quality of institutions refers to the effectiveness and integrity of the organization and system that governs society. It includes factors such as compliance with legal regulations, governance structures, accountability and the rule of law. High institutional quality is often associated with better economic performance, as it improves investor confidence and governance. Studies show that openness to trade and democratic practices can have a substantial bearing on the worth of institutions. El-Helaly (2020), view institutional quality as the effectiveness, efficiency, and integrity of institutions and government in their roles at fulfilling their societal responsibilities. Based on the foregoing, high quality institutions are characterized by the ability of stakeholders to sustain the rule of law, enforce contracts, guard property rights, human rights, maintain transparency, reduce corruption and foster social and economic development.

2.1.5. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

According to Sovbetov and Moussa (2025). FDI is an investment done by corporations or individuals in foreign companies across borders in business interests. Foreign direct investment usually involves the founding of corporate processes or the procurement of business assets, such as possession or control of foreign companies. According to Kwame and Kwame (2022), FDI, is the capital outlay by an individual, corporation or unit from one nation into the business or assets of a different nation. Javed et al, (2024), submit that FDI differs from portfolio investments, which is a mere purchase of stock or bonds, that FDI involves a substantial degree of control and ownership share in the foreign company; that could include acquiring equity stake of at least 10% of the voting shares or establishing offices, factories or even subsidiaries.

2.2. Empirical review

Al-Tuwaijari et al. (2025) examined the effect of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption on foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, while also assessing the moderating influence of institutional quality. Using panel data from 22 MENA countries covering 2002–2022, the study employed several econometric techniques, including panel OLS, DOLS, FMOLS, GMM, and bias-corrected Least Square Dummy Variable (LSDVC) estimations. The findings indicate that IFRS adoption contributes positively to FDI inflows; however, its effectiveness largely depends on the strength of institutional frameworks. The study concludes that accounting reforms alone are insufficient and should be accompanied by broader institutional improvements to maximize their impact on investment attraction.

Galli and Olarinde (2024) analyzed the effect of institutional quality and macroeconomic policies on domestic private investment across sixty countries from 2005–2021 using PCA and dynamic GMM. The findings show that governance quality significantly influences investment in high- and middle-income countries, while property rights matter mainly in low-income economies. Macroeconomic factors such as GDP growth, trade openness, and exchange rates also affect investment across income groups. Additionally, foreign direct investment crowds in domestic investment in middle-income countries but crowds it out in high-income economies. The study highlights the importance of good governance and sound macroeconomic policies in promoting domestic private investment.

Javed et al. (2024) This study investigated the relationship between IFRS adoption and FDI in Afghanistan from 2003 to 2020 by means of panel integration and causality analysis. Results revealed a significant positive relationship between IFRS acceptance and FDI inflows, indicating that IFRS-based transparency enhances both short-term economic growth and long-term diversification. The study concludes that IFRS-driven FDI can serve as a catalyst for economic development in emerging economies. Even though the study was carried out in a foreign land, but it is a developing economy from where the current study can draw insight from.

Jinapor et al. (2024) investigates whether institutional quality (INSQY) can mitigate the environmental impacts of foreign direct investment (FDI) and industrialization in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Using panel data from 45 SSA countries (2000–2019) and the Driscoll–Kraay estimation technique, it was discovered that FDI and industrialization generally harm environmental quality, while institutional quality directly improves it. Importantly, strong institutions help reduce the negative environmental effects of FDI and industrial activities. The study recommends strengthening institutional capacity and enforcing environmental regulations to ensure sustainable development while encouraging industrialization and foreign investment.

Khan et al. (2024) examined the relationship between institutional quality and foreign direct investment (FDI) using a two-step system Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) across developed, developing, and Asian economies from 2002–2019. The results reveal that regulatory

quality significantly promotes FDI in the global sample, while other institutional indicators show mixed or negative effects. In developing economies, political stability, voice and accountability, and corruption control positively influence FDI inflows. Conversely, some governance indicators reduce investment in certain regions. Although the study highlights the importance of institutional frameworks in attracting FDI, it adopts a global perspective and offers limited country-specific policy guidance

Silue (2024) examines how institutional quality influences the relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. The data were analyzed using annual panel data from 30 countries in the region covering the period 2000–2020. The empirical investigation applies the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimation technique to evaluate the relationship among the variables. The findings indicate that FDI contributes positively to economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa, and this impact becomes stronger in countries with higher levels of institutional quality; and domestic investment is found to significantly promote economic growth. However, trade openness and inflation do not show statistically significant effects on economic growth in the region. This study did not recommend a way forward.

Sinibi et al. (2023) Using data from 15 African countries (1994–2014) and applying GMM and Propensity Score Matching (PSM) techniques, this study examined the moderating role of institutional quality in the relationship between IFRS adoption and Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI). Findings show that weak institutional frameworks in Africa negatively affect the IFRS–FPI relationship. The study emphasizes that strong institutional development is crucial for realizing the benefits of IFRS adoption.

Nejad et al. (2018) Analyzing data from 10 ASEAN countries between 2001 and 2016 with the bias-corrected LSDVC estimator, revealed a positive association between IFRS adoption and FDI inflows. The results suggest that harmonized reporting standards attract foreign investors by improving transparency and comparability. The authors recommend that countries yet to adopt IFRS should do so to encourage FDI inflows.

Udofia (2018) The study assessed the impact of IFRS adoption on intercontinental investments in Nigeria (2007–2016) using a mixed-method design. While IFRS adoption positively influenced investors' perceptions and improved reporting quality, FDI and FPI growth were higher before adoption. The study concludes that IFRS alone cannot drive investment growth without improvements in institutional, legal, and macroeconomic conditions.

Ugwu and Okoye (2018) Focusing on Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa, this study analyzed the impact of FDI on economic growth after IFRS adoption using secondary data and dummy variable regression. Results show that FDI positively affected GDP in Nigeria and Ghana but negatively in South Africa. Post-IFRS adoption, Nigeria's FDI impact declined. The study concludes that IFRS adoption alone is insufficient and that supportive institutional and infrastructural frameworks are essential for sustainable FDI-driven growth.

2.3. Theoretical Framework

2.3.1. Investment theory

Investment Theory Investment theory explains the processes and motivations underlying investment decisions, emphasizing factors that shape investor behavior and national economic outcomes. Hussein and Haque (2016) identified a strong correlation between FDI, trade, and GDP progress in Bangladesh, showing how global trade fluctuations affect national economic performance. Similarly, Sengupta and Puri (2020) highlighted the integration of foreign exchange assets into India's budget framework as evidence of their role in economic consolidation. Empirical evidence that specifically supports FDI promotion of economic growth and development views (Agboli, 2021; Kim & Ahn, 2020) especially in regions with limited domestic capital. However, its impact tends to be weaker in high-income economies such as the United States, where domestic investment dominates. In Afghanistan, IFRS adoption has been recognized as a strategic initiative to attract FDI and stimulate long-term economic growth, underscoring the need to assess the true effect of IFRS on both FDI inflows and national development.

2.3.2. Institutional theory

Proponent and Year The modern development of institutional theory in organizational studies is commonly attributed to John W. Meyer and Brian Rowan (1977), who argued that organizations adopt formal structures to gain legitimacy within institutional environments. Later, Paul J. DiMaggio and Walter W. Powell (1983) expanded the theory by introducing the concept of institutional isomorphism, explaining why organizations in similar environments tend to become alike. Institutional theory explains how organizations adopt structures, policies, and practices in response to pressures from their external environment in order to gain legitimacy, stability, and acceptance within society. The theory suggests that organizations often conform to established rules, norms, and cultural expectations such as laws, professional standards, and social values—rather than relying solely on efficiency or economic considerations. In the context of accounting and finance, institutional theory helps explain why firms adopt practices like International Financial Reporting Standards to align with global norms and gain credibility with investors and regulators.

3. Methodology

This study is a descriptive research design spanning a nine-year period (2015–2023), corresponding with Nigeria's IFRS adoption timeline. Secondary data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) publications and the Worldwide Governance Indicators database. Variables include IFRS adoption, foreign direct investment in equity, money market portfolio, trade credit, control of corruption, and political stability. The Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) panel regression technique was applied for data analysis.

3.1. Model specification

The following model has been adopted for this study, taken from the studies of Matthew et al. (2017) and Bamanga et al. (2019).

$$FDE_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IFRSA_t + \beta_2 PSt + \beta_3 CCr + \beta_4 FDe + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots i$$

$$FPM_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IFRSA_t + \beta_2 PSt + \beta_3 CCr + \beta_4 FPM + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots ii$$

$$FSC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IFRSA_t + \beta_2 PSt + \beta_3 CCr + \beta_4 FSC + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots iii$$

Where;

- FDE_t – Represents Foreign Direct Investment in equity over a 9-year period.
- FPM_t – Denotes Foreign Portfolio Investment in the money market across 9 years.
- FSC_t – Refers to Foreign Direct Investment in trade (suppliers’) credit over 9 years.
- IFRSA_t – Indicates the level of IFRS adoption within the 9-year study period.
- PSt – Captures the influence of political stability on IFRS adoption over 9 years.
- CCr – Measures the effect of corruption control on IFRS adoption during the same period.
- FDE₋₁ – Represents the lagged value of Foreign Direct Investment in equity.
- FPM₋₁ – Refers to the lagged value of Foreign Portfolio Investment in the money market.
- FSC₋₁ – Denotes the lagged value of Foreign Direct Investment in suppliers’ credit.
- β₁–β₄ – Coefficients of regression parameters.
- ε – Error term accounting for unexplained variations in the model.

3.2. Justification for the model

The study utilized the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) using time series approach. This allows Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows to model as dynamic variable by incorporating their lagged values into the regression equation. The inclusion of the lagged dependent variable helps to minimize autocorrelation issues commonly found in time-series analyses. In addition, the GMM method effectively addresses endogeneity problems, thereby yielding more reliable and efficient estimates compared to several other estimation techniques. The analysis covers a nine-year period (2015–2023), selected to capture the timeframe corresponding with Nigeria’s adoption of IFRS.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	CCr	FDE_1	FSC	FSC_1	FDE	FMM	FMM_1	IFRS	PST
Mean	-1.13056	1.62879	5.975085	0.576600	1442.55	1893.414	3.471	1.00	-1.9929
Median	-1.08372	1.5555	3.46136	0.840339	644.133	1075.018	3.746	1.00	-1.9431
Max	-1.02960	2.03632	22.26876	1.66766	5910.41	4731.717	3.940	1.00	-1.8777
Min	-1.27471	1.495489	0.000000	-0.775870	521.521	271.9179	3.012	1.00	-2.1302
Std. Dev.	0.091985	0.378446	16.41759	0.869320	3962.082	1546.334	0.427	0.00	0.0941
Jarque-Bera	0.755776	3.710194	1.802095	0.501345	5.895693	1.005622	1.052	NA	0.6786
Prob	0.45687	0.10429	0.27076	0.51885	0.052453	0.40322	0.3940	NA	0.4748

Source: Author’s calculation via EViews 10

Table 1. showed the summary description of variables that: the effect of control of corruption is normally distributed with a probability of 0.45687 and an average mean of -1.130560, a median of -1.083716, the maximum control of corruption is -1.029604, while the minimum control is -1.274705, this showed that corruption control in Nigeria is being given attention, verified by the closer it is to positive value as seen in the maximum value. The foreign direct investment in equity lag has a normal probability distribution of 0.10429, a mean value of 1.62879, median of 1.5555, a maximum investment lag of ₦2.03632billion and a minimum of ₦1.495489billion. The foreign direct investment in supplier credits has a normally distributed probability of 0.27076, while the maximum investment in suppliers' credits in Nigeria within the period understudy is ₦22.26876billion, the zero minimum investment arose as a result of no foreign direct investment in suppliers' credit in 2015 in Nigeria. The foreign direct investment in suppliers' credit lag is distributed normally with a probability of 0.51885, with a maximum value of 1.66766 and a minimum of -0.775870, the result from the table revealed that Nigeria has a maximum foreign direct investment in equity of ₦5910.41billion and a minimum value of ₦521.521billion, this presented a mean value of 1442.55 and a probability of 0.052453. The foreign investment in money market is distributed normally with a probability value of 0.40322, a mean of 1893.414, a standard deviation of 1546.334, the maximum investment is ₦4731.717billion with a minimum of ₦271.9179billion. finally, the study also revealed that political stability effects is distributed normally with a probability of 0.4748, a mean of -1.9929 and a median of -1.9431. the maximum political stability effect is -1.8777, while the minimum value is -2.1302; this indicates that Nigeria political stability effort is on the positive as seen in the maximum value which tends towards positivity. The higher the positive indicator the better.

Table 2. Multicollinearity Test

V I F Test

Var	Coefficient Var	Un-centered VIF	Centered VIF
PST	1.36E+08	3.459612	0.660642
CCr	8.55E+07	0.7017595	3.5594165
FMM_1	1,496,427	11.67938	1.4893795
FDIE1	555,425	3.8122825	4.359739
FSC_1	118,054.9	7.39917	4.8895605
C	4.07E+08	26.031405	NIL

Source: Author's calculation via EViews 10

Table 2 Shows that the variance inflation factor (VIF) showed lenience values that are steadily lower than 10, which connotes the absence of multicollinearity amongst the independent variables, it is therefore, fit for the estimate.

Table 3. Correlation Matrix

	FDE	PST	CCr	FDE1
FDE	1.000000			
PST	-0.151135	1.000000		
CCr	-0.1312695	0.494596	1.000000	
FDE1	0.488228	-0.217297	-0.205125	1.000000

Source: Author's calculation via EViews 10

From Table 3, FDE has a negative relationship of (-0.151135) with the PST, a negative association of (-0.1312695) with CCr, but a positive association of (0.488228) with FDE_I; whereas; PST_IFRS reported a positive association of (0.494596) with CCr but a negative relationship of (-0.217297) with FDE_I, the relationship between CCr and FDEI showed a negative value of (-0.205125). The above associations depict that there are no multi-collinear relationships among the variables since all the associations are less than 80% acceptable benchmark.

Table 4. Normality test

Series:	RESID01
Sample:	2015-2023
Mean	1.11e-16
Median	1.01e-15
Max	-1.01e-15
Mini	1.01e-15
Std Deviation	-3.33e-16
Skewness	4.58e-16
Kurtosis	1.191663
Jarque-Bera	3.458694
Prob.	2.208991
	0.331378

Source: Author's calculation via EViews 10

Table 4 is a check for the normality of residuals from the regression line, which is a combination of the transformed and standardized total observations of the study. The report showed a Jarque-Bera stat-value of 2.208991 with a corresponding probability value of 0.331378 or (33.14%). The null hypothesis of normality is accepted as the P-value at 33.14% is more than 5% critical value. The implication is that the population residue is normally distributed, fulfilling the good regression line assumption.

Table 5: Heteroskedasticity Test (Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey)

F-Stat	44.34545	Prob. F (6,1)	0.0602
Obs*R ²	3.49213	Prob. Chi ² (6)	0.1109
Scaled Exp SS	0.02454	Prob. Chi ² (6)	0.5001

From Table 5, Obs. R-squared showed a value of 3.49213 with a matching probability outcome of 0.1109, apparently more than 0.05 benchmark, this indicates that there is no heteroskedasticity in the residuals, and it is desirable.

Table 6: GMM Regression for Model One

Dependent Variable: FDE

Method: Generalized Method of Moments

Date: 09/15/25; Time: 15:22

Sample:17

Standard errors & covariance computed using estimation weighting matrix Instrument specification: IFRS PST CCr FDE1

Var	Coeff	Std. Error	t-Stat	Proby.
IFRS	-205.066109	171,3858	-1.1965175	0.06955
PST	-7541.24695	4860.078	-1.551672	0.0450
CCr	9457.37	5198.33	1.819309	0.00385
FDE1	2778.759	207.246	13.40802	0.0028
C	-12507.385	3503.4595	-3.57001	0.0380
R ²	0.992524	Mean Dept Var		2884.111
Adj R ²	0.977571	S.D. Dep Var		3962.082
S.E. of Reg	593.3765	Sum ² Resid		704191.3
D-W Stat	2.662689	J-Stat		0.000000
Instrument rank	5			

Source: Author's calculation via EViews 10

The R² value of 0.992524 shows that 99.25% proportion of sample variation in the dependent variable; *Investment in equity* was clarified by the describing variables, while 0.75% are explained by other variables or the error terms The adjusted R² of 97.76% indicates that the regression line captured more than 97% of total variation in IFRS caused by variations in the explanatory variable as specified in the model equation, with about 2.24% representing the error term. The J-stat value of 0.0000, indicates that the model is well fitted for the estimate, and that the explanatory variable jointly has significant effect on IFRS adoption for the population of the study.

The first model was formulated based on the initial objective of the study, which examined the hypothesis that the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) is void of significant relationship with foreign investment in equity. The results confirmed this assertion, showing a p-value of (0.06955 > 0.05), implying that IFRS acceptance in Nigeria lack significant effects on foreign equity investment inflows. However, political stability exhibited a negative but significant effect on equity investment inflows, with a p-value of (0.0450 < 0.05). In contrast, control of corruption demonstrated a positive and significant influence on foreign equity investment, as indicated by a p-value of (0.00385 < 0.05). This suggests that effective corruption control can enhance investor confidence and attract equity investments into the country. Additionally, the lagged value of equity investment was found to have a positive and significant

effect (p -value = 0.0028 < 0.05), implying that past investment performance contributes to current inflows. The inclusion of this lagged variable serves to capture the dynamic nature of investment behavior and minimize potential estimation errors.

Table 7: GMM Regression for Model Two

Dependent Variable: FMM

Method: Generalized Method of Moment

Date: 09/15/25 Time: 16:37

Sample:17

Standard errors & covariance computed using estimation

weighting matrix Instrument specification: IFRS PST

CCr MM_1

Var	Coeff	Std. Error	t-Stat	Proby
IFRS	264.3377	185.8198	1.422549	0.14540
PST	-7384.493	7223.605	-1.022273	0.00245
CCr	10674.795	8148.58	1.310019	0.0600
FMM_1	1394.300	487.14565	2.862184	0.0146
C	-21825.93	6914.805	-3.156406	0.0121
R ²	0.946422	Mean Dep Var		1893.414
Adj R ²	0.839265	S.D. dependent var		1546.334
S.E. of Reg	619.9522	Sum ² Resid		768681.5
D-W Stat	2.645228	J-Stat		0.0000
Instrument rank	5			

The R² value of 0.946422 shows that 94.64% of the sample variance in the dependent variable; *investment in money market* was clarified by the explanatory variables, while 5.36% are explained by other variables or the error terms. The adjusted R² of 83.93% indicates that the regression line captured more than 83% of total variation in IFRS caused by variations in the explanatory variable as specified in the model equation, with about 16.07% representing the error term. The J-stat value of 0.0000, implying the model is fit for the estimate, and that the explanatory variable jointly has significant effect on IFRS adoption for the population of the study.

The model is derived from the second objective of the study which addresses the conjecture that says international financial reporting standard lack significant relationship with foreign investment in money market. In this case it is so IFRS showed positive insignificant relationship with investment in money market with a p -value of (0.14540 > 0.05); meaning that the adoption of IFRS in Nigeria does not have any significant effect on investment inflows into the money market in Nigeria. Political stability effect is shown to have negative but significant influence on investment inflow into the money market as seen in the p -value of (0.00245 < 0.05); control of corruption showed an insignificant positive effect on investment inflow into the money market with a p -value of (0.0600 > 0.05), meaning that corruption control has little or no effect in investors' interest in

Nigeria. The investment in money market lag showed a positive significant effect on foreign investment in money market with a p-value of ($0.0146 < 0.05$); this lag is used as a dynamic model to regulate to adjust for irregular data points/outliers and reduce errors in the model.

Table 8: GMM Regression for Model Three

Dependent Variable: FSC

Method: Generalized Method of Moments

Date: 09/15/25 Time: 17:41

Sample: 17

Standard errors & covariance computed using estimation

weighting matrix Instrument specification: IFRS PST CCr

FSC_1

Var	Coeff	Std. Error	t-Stat	Proby
IFRS	-11.937256	8.685395	-1.3744056	0.0554
PST	271.447664	138.0958	1.9656475	0.0045
CCr	-238.01157	127.6067	-1.8651965	0.03245
FSC_1	11.415911	6.143175	1.858308	0.0027
C	275.742672	137.65965	2.0030755	0.0285
R ²	0.933524	Mean dep var		11.95017
Adj R ²	0.800573	S.D. dep var		16.41759
S.E. of Reg.	7.331643	Sum ² Resid		107.5060
D-W Stat	1.963979	J-Stat.		0.0000
Instrument rank	5			

The R² value of 0.933524 shows that 93.35% of the sample variance in the dependent variable; *investment in suppliers' credit* was explained by the independent variables, while 6.65% are explained by other variables or the error terms. The adjusted R² of 80.06% indicates that the regression line captured more than 80% of total variation in FSC caused by variations in the explanatory variable as specified in the model equation, with about 19.94% representing the error term. The J-statistics value of 0.0000, indicates that the model is well fitted for the estimate, and that the explanatory variable jointly has significant effect on FSC for the population of the study.

The model, derived from the third objective of this research, which examines the proposition that International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) have no significant relationship with foreign investment in suppliers' credit. The findings confirm this assumption, as IFRS adoption displayed a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with investment inflows in suppliers' credit ($p = 0.08540 > 0.05$). This suggests that the implementation of IFRS in Nigeria does not meaningfully influence such investment inflows. However, political stability showed a positive and significant impact on suppliers' credit investment ($p = 0.0045 < 0.05$), while control of corruption exhibited a negative but significant effect ($p = 0.0345 < 0.05$), indicating that effective anti-corruption

measures strongly affect investors' decisions. Additionally, the lagged value of suppliers' credit investment had a positive and significant influence ($p = 0.0027 < 0.05$), serving as a dynamic model component that helps reduce estimation errors and control for outliers.

4.1. Discussion of findings

The outcome of the study presents pivotal understandings on how the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), institutional quality, and foreign direct investment (FDI) interact in Nigeria. The results indicate that IFRS implementation alone lack notable effect on FDI inflows; instead, its impact is strengthened when supported by other influences such as political stability and effective corruption control. This suggests that the advantages of IFRS particularly its role in improving financial transparency and comparability—can only attract more foreign investment when reinforced by sound governance systems and a stable political climate.

With respect to the first objective to establish the stable nature of the political environment in enhancing IFRS adoption benefits regarding equity investment, the analysis shows that IFRS acceptance is negatively correlated to investment inflows, although the relationship is insignificant statistically. This discovery is consistent with the results of Khan et al. (2024), Bamanga et al. (2019) contradicts Al-Tuwaijari et al. (2025), and Nejad et al. (2018), who reported a positive and significant link. The implication is that while IFRS promotes transparency, it does not automatically enhance investors' confidence unless political and institutional conditions are favorable. Political stability showed a negative but significant effect on equity investment inflows, consistent with Nejad et al. (2018) and Beneish et al. (2015), indicating that political uncertainty discourages long-term equity commitments. Conversely, control of corruption exhibited a positive and significant effect, suggesting that reducing corruption can strengthen investor confidence and improve equity market participation.

From the second objective of the study, which is to determine the Nigerian institutional quality and reliability in attracting and encouraging FDI for economic development; for money market investments, IFRS adoption demonstrated a positive but insignificant relationship, corroborating Sinibi et al. (2023) and Silue (2024), but diverging from Bamanga et al. (2019). Political stability again exhibited a negative significant influence, while control of corruption showed a positive but insignificant effect. These findings suggest that while investors recognize the regulatory improvements brought by IFRS, persistent political instability remains a major deterrent to short-term financial investments.

The third objective which is to analyze the strength of domestic institutions in enhancing the enabling environment for investment potentials; in the case of suppliers' credit, the acceptance of IFRS showed a negative insignificant affiliation, consistent with Sinibi et al. (2023) but contradicting Matthew et al. (2017) and Al-Tuwaijari et al. (2025). Political stability, however, displayed a positive significant effect, implying that a stable business climate encourages suppliers to extend credit facilities, this agrees with the findings of Khan et al., (2024). On the other hand,

control of corruption had a negative significant effect, suggesting that excessive regulatory or bureaucratic controls associated with anti-corruption efforts may create operational bottlenecks that discourage supplier financing.

Overall, the findings confirm that IFRS adoption, while essential for promoting financial transparency, must be complemented by strong institutional frameworks and political stability to effectively attract and retain foreign investors. The results highlight the critical need for Nigeria to strengthen its governance systems, ensure consistent policy implementation, and maintain a stable socio-political environment to maximize the benefits of IFRS and foster sustainable diaspora inflow of investment.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the role of institutional strength in enhancing the effect of international financial reporting standards on FDI attraction in Nigeria. The findings reveal that IFRS adoption alone does not exert a significant direct influence on FDI inflows. Rather, its effectiveness depends largely on the broader institutional and governance environment within which it operates. In particular, political stability and effective corruption control were found to play crucial roles in determining whether the transparency and comparability benefits associated with IFRS translate into increased foreign investment.

The results further indicate that while IFRS adoption contributes to improvements in financial reporting quality, investors are more responsive to institutional signals such as governance credibility, regulatory effectiveness, and the predictability of the political environment. Across the different components of foreign investment examined equity inflows, money market investments, and suppliers' credit the impact of IFRS varied, but institutional factors consistently influenced investment behavior. Political instability was observed to discourage long-term and short-term investment flows, whereas stronger corruption control mechanisms enhanced investor confidence in certain contexts.

Overall, the study concludes that accounting reforms such as IFRS adoption should not be pursued as isolated policy instruments for attracting foreign investment. Instead, they must be supported by comprehensive institutional reforms that strengthen governance quality, enhance regulatory efficiency, and ensure political stability. For Nigeria to fully realize the potential benefits of IFRS in attracting foreign capital, policymakers must focus on improving institutional credibility and maintaining a stable economic and political environment capable of sustaining investor confidence and long-term investment inflows.

6. Recommendations

- 1) Political environmental stability must be continually maintained and corruption systematically controlled so as to take advantage of the benefits of IFRS adoption.

- 2) There should be an emphasis on high quality institutions that is strong, reliable with high level competence and integrity that encourages foreign direct investments, that potentially enhances national economic development.
- 3) Domestic institutions should be strengthened and encouraged so as to create the enabling environment for the implementation of monetary policy that attracts investment in the money market which is the driving force in any economy.

7. Suggestion for further Studies

The study suggests that the role of institutional strength in enhancing the effect of international financial reporting standards on FDI attraction in Nigeria can be studied further by adding some more variables, extending the period beyond 9 years, and also choosing specific institutions to assess and test the findings of this study, so as to have wider base for comparison and also to add to the body of existing literature to enhance the robustness of this area of study.

References

- Aanu, S., & Mary, O. (2016). IFRS Adoption and foreign direct investment: Evidence from Nigerian Quoted Firms,7(2),99-105.<https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2016.v7n2p99>
- Adeleye, B. N., Adedoyin, F. F., & Nathaniel, S. (2021). The criticality of ICT infrastructure in attracting foreign direct investment: Evidence from developing economies. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 48(4), 629–648. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JES-04-2020-0173>
- Adetula, D. T., Nwobu, O., & Owolabi, F. (2014). International financial reporting standards and foreign direct investment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management (IJCBM)*, 3(3),446-449. <https://www.researchgate.net/>
- Agboli, M. (2021). Economic growth and macroeconomic transformation in developing economies. *African Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 3(2), 1–15. <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Ajibade, A. T., Okere, W., Isiaka, M. A., & Mabinuori, O. (2019). International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) Adoption and Foreign Direct Investments (FDI): A Comparative Analysis of Nigeria and Ghana, *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 11(2),1-10. <https://doi.org.10.9734/ajeba/2019/v11i230122>
- Akpomi, M. E., & Nnadi, M. A. (2017). The impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) Adoption on Foreign Direct Investments (FDI): Evidence from Africa and Implications for Managers of Education. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management* ISSN 2504-8856 .3(2). <https://www.researchgate.net/>

- Al-Tuwaijari, M. R., Rahman, M. R., Ahmad, A., & Rahim, R. (2025). Effect of IFRS adoption and institutional quality in FDI attraction in MENA countries. *Journal of Management World*, 2025(2), 268–279. <https://doi.org/10.53935/jomw.v2024i4.911>
- Bamanga, B. M., Gadi, U. T., Ologhodo, J. C., Ekawu, A. S., Dalyop, L. M., Ojofedo. U. D., et al., (2019). Moderating effect of institutional quality on the relationship between international financial reporting standards (IFRS) adoption and foreign direct investment in Nigeria. Research report by Ph.D Accounting Students, Department of Accounting; Nasarawa State University, Keffi.
- Beneish, M. D., Miller, B. P., & Yohn, T. I., (2015). Macroeconomics evidence on the impact of mandatory IFRS on equity and debt markets. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*. 34(1), 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccpubpol.2014.10.002>
- Boateng, A., Hua, X., Nisar, S., & Wu, J. (2021). Examining the determinants of inward FDI: The role of institutional quality and governance. *International Business Review*, 30(3), 101–115.
- DiMaggio, P. J., & Powell, W. W. (1983). The iron cage revisited: Institutional isomorphism and collective rationality in organizational fields. *American Sociological Review*, 48(2), 147–160. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2095101>
- Emalereta, M. (2017). The impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) Adoption on Foreign Direct Investments (FDI): Evidence from Africa and Implications for Managers of Education, 3(2). <https://www.researchgate.net/>
- Efobi, U. R. (2017). International financial reporting standard, trade and Foreign direct investment in Sub-Sahara African countries. A thesis submitted to the school of postgraduate studies of covenant university, Ota, Ogun state, Nigeria <http://eprints.covenantuniversity.edu.ng/id/eprint/9524>
- El-Helaly, M. A., (2020). Diffusion theory, national corruption and IFRS adoption around the world. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*. 38; 100305. <https://www.researchgate.net/>
- Estimation, D. P. (2017). Relationship between Institutional Factors and FDI Flows in Developing Countries: New Evidence. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies5020017>

- Houqe, M. N., Reza M. M., & Zijl, T., (2024). The influence of IFRS and institutional quality on economic growth. *Cogent Economics & Finance*. 12(1), 2396547. <https://www.tandfonline.com>
- Galli, S. M., & Olarinde, M. O. (2024). Institutional quality and macroeconomic policies impact on domestic private investment: Evidence from high, middle, and low-income countries. *UMYU Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*, 7(1). [https://doi.org/10.61143/umyu-jafr.7\(1\)2024.009](https://doi.org/10.61143/umyu-jafr.7(1)2024.009)
- Hussain, M. E., & Haque, M. (2016). Foreign direct investment, trade, and economic growth: An empirical analysis of Bangladesh. *Economies*, 4(2), 7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies4020007>
- Istiak, K., Cummings, J. R., Forrester, R., & Adams, M., (2024). Examining the Impact of Vulnerability and the Law of Justice on the IFRS Adoption Decision. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*. 17(9), 417. <https://www.mdpi.com>
- Javed, S., Nazir, S., Malik, G. M., Khan, A. A., & Jalil, S. (2024). Sustainable Practice of IFRS and Economic Growth: Evidence from A Case Study on A Developing Country. *Innovation Economics Frontiers*, 27(2), 57-70. <https://doi.org/10.36923/iefrontiers>.
- Jinapor, J. A., Abor, J. Y., & Graham, M. (2024). FDI, industrialisation and environmental quality in Sub-Saharan Africa: The role of institutional quality. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11, 1484. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-024-04000-6>
- Kapellas, K., & Siougle, G. (2018). The Effect of IFRS Adoption on Investment Management: *A Hague Review of the Literature*, 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ti.2018.91001>
- Kim, J., & Ahn, S. (2020). Economic growth and productive capacity: A conceptual review. *African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research*, 8(3), 149–166. <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Khan, H., Dong, Y., & Bibi, R. (2024). Institutional quality and foreign direct investment: Global evidence. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 15(3), 10547–10591. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-023-01508-1>
- Kwame A. T. & Kwame A. O. (2022). The effect of IFRS adoption on bank internationalization. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*. 27(3), 2932–2945. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com>

- Kurul, Z., & Yalta, A. Y. (2017). Relationship between Institutional Factors and FDI Flows in Developing Countries: New Evidence from Dynamic Panel Estimation. *Economies*, MPI,5,17; <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies5020017>
- Matthew, G. O. Y., Ashikin, N.S. M., Suppiah, S.D.K., & Law, S. H. (2017). IFRS Adoption Institutional Quality and Foreign Direct Investment Inflows: A Dynamic Panel Analysis,10(2),43-76.
- Meyer, J. W., & Rowan, B. (1977). Institutionalized organizations: Formal structure as myth and ceremony. *American Journal of Sociology*, 83(2), 340–363. <https://doi.org/10.1086/226550>
- Nejad, M. Y., Ahmad, A., Mdsalleh, F., & Rahim, R. A. (2018). IFRS Adoption and Foreign Direct Investment: An Application of the LSDVC Estimator, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/32723040/>
- Nzube, C.J. & Emmanuel, A., (2018). Impact of international financial reporting standards (IFRS) on foreign direct investment drive (FDI) in Nigeria: A case study of Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) branch Port-Harcourt. *International Journal of Business and Economics and Entrepreneurship Development in Africa*. 10(6), 20-32. <https://www.arcnjournals.org/>
- Radu, M., (2015). Political Stability - A Condition for Sustainable Growth in Romania. *Procedia Economics and Finance*. 30:751-757. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)01324-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)01324-6)
- Samaha K., & Khlif, H. (2016). Adoption of and compliance with IFRS in developing countries. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*. 6(1):33-49. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAEE-02-2013-0011>
- Sengupta, P., & Puri, R. (2020). Exploration of relationship between FDI and GDP: A comparison between India and its neighboring countries. *Global Business Review*, 21(2), 473-489. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150918760026S>
- Sherman, T., & Klerk, M. De. (2015). International financial reporting standards and foreign ownership in South African companies, 19(1),72-88. <https://doi.org/10.25159/1998-8125/5834>
- Silue, D. (2024). Institutional quality, FDI and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa: A two-step system GMM estimation. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Research*, 8(5). <https://doi.org/10.51505/IJEBMR.2024.8504>

- Sinibi, C., Arendse, J. A., & Khumalo, S. A., (2023). IFRS and FPI nexus: does the quality of the institutional framework matter for African countries? *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economics*. 13(1), 195-215. <https://doi.org.10.1108/jaee>.
- Sovbetov, Y., & Moussa, M. (2025). Interaction of economic freedom and foreign direct investment globally: Evidence from neglected regions. *International Economic Studies*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2512.01695>
- Udofia, I.E., (2018). IFRS adoption and cross border investment in Nigeria *Journal of Accounting and Management Information Systems*. 17(4); 605-625. <https://dx.doi.org.10.24818/jamis>. from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330187138_IFRS_adoption_and_cross_border_investment_in_Nigeria
- Ugwu, J. I., & Okoye, E. I. (2018). Accounting for the Effect of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth, Post IFRS Adoption in Selected Sub-Saharan African Countries (1999-2015), *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*,8(2),70-99. <https://dx.doi.org.10.6007/ijarbss/>.
- UNCTAD, (2016b). World Investment Report, Annex Table, UN reports foreign direct Investment. Unctad.org/en/pages/DIAE/world-investment-report.